

Research Article

Models based on chronological data correctly predict the spread of freshwater aliens, and reveal a strong influence of river access, anthropogenic activities and climate regimes

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Abstract

Alien species constitute one of the main threats to freshwater ecosystems, negatively impacting biodiversity, economy, biosecurity and ecosystem services. Predicting the arrival and spread of alien species is of paramount importance to prevent new introductions and control the expansion and establishment of already introduced species. We modelled the distribution of four freshwater invaders in Great Britain, using environmental and anthropogenic predictors, to help focus management actions. The species grouped different taxa including signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), the marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*), the red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*) and the pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*). The modelling approach accounted for methodological limitations and implemented two evaluations, a temporal evaluation using data corresponding to 70% of the oldest records to calibrate models and the remaining 30% for evaluation using various performance metrics (the common AUC, TSS and also null models) and an independent evaluation using the most recent range expansion of the species in the last six years. The distribution of the species was facilitated by multiple environmental and anthropogenic predictors. Road density was the second most important predictor of the occurrence of signal crayfish and red-eared slider preceded by the distance to ports and isothermality for each species respectively. Human population density was the most important predictor of marsh frog presence whereas pike-perch was mostly related to the proximity of boat ramps and precipitation regimes. Our distribution models were accurate and predicted the most recent range expansion of all of the species, highlighting their usefulness for preventing alien species spread and the value of using historical projections, usually available for non-native species, to calibrate and evaluate Species Distribution Models.

Key words: aquatic non-native species, human ecology, introduction pathways, management, species distribution models, forecasting

Introduction

Freshwater ecosystems are among the most endangered ecosystems on the planet (Sala et al. 2000; Tickner et al. 2020), yet they tend to be neglected by conservation efforts compared to terrestrial or marine ecosystems (Darwall et al. 2011). Biological invasions are of special concern in freshwater ecosystems, threatening the native biodiversity by disrupting trophic links (Gallardo et al. 2016) or competing with species of commercial interest (Cardona et al. 2008), and also impacting the economy (Cuthbert et al. 2021) and human health (Tricarico et al. 2017; Mazza and Tricarico 2018). Information about the dispersal patterns and vectors of invasion is crucial to predict the invasion process of different species, for which appropriate models are essential (Barbet-Massin et al. 2018). Once an alien species has arrived in a new area or country, secondary dispersal may occur naturally or via human transport (Johnson et al. 2001; Vander Zanden et al. 2008), but for many organisms assessing the relative contribution of each of these factors is difficult (Huang et al. 2017). Therefore, understanding this post-introduction range expansion is critical to control the further spread of introduced species (Mallez and McCartney 2018; Robertson et al. 2020).

In addition to the importance of climate on the distribution of alien freshwater species (Rahel and Olden 2008), recent research has shown that anthropogenic factors can affect the range expansion more than environmental variables alone (Faurby and Araújo 2018; Chapman et al. 2020). For example, the number of invasive species tends to be higher outside protected areas than inside them, possibly reflecting the role of anthropogenic pressures (Gallardo et al. 2015; Moustakas et al. 2018). Multiple intentional introductions in distant localities are also common and can increase invasion success (Signorile et al. 2016; Huang et al. 2017), for example, most alien fishes in Great Britain have increased their numbers in the last decade (Copp et al. 2006) due to both accidental and deliberate releases (Zięba et al. 2010). A similar pattern exists for alien molluscs (Sousa et al. 2014) and pet turtles such as the red-eared slider, whose high establishment success has been aided by repeated introductions around the globe (Bomford et al. 2008). Therefore, combining anthropogenic and environmental types of variables in ecological models will help to obtain accurate predictions that support cost-effective management solutions which are usually challenging at large spatial scales (Glen et al. 2013).

Species Distribution Modelling (SDM) is a valuable tool that uses spatially explicit variables to explain and predict the range expansion of alien species and provide options for management actions (Guisan et al. 2013). However, SDM reliability to correctly predict the spread of the species has been questioned based on limitations such as lack of equilibrium of the species in the invaded ecosystems (Václavík and Meentemeyer 2012; Mainali et al. 2015), data restrictions and errors (Václavík and Meentemeyer 2009; Barbet-Massin et al. 2012), shortcomings of the performance metrics (Jiménez-Valverde 2012) or difficulties in the evaluation process (Warren et al. 2020). In fact, the evaluation step in SDM is key and requires independent distribution data which is, for most species rarely available (West et al. 2016), thus discrimination metrics are obtained through a data splitting approach [usually cross-validation (Helmstetter et al. 2021)] creating a training and testing dataset with randomly selected records from the total occurrence set. This type of evaluation has some limitations and has been criticised due to overestimation (Lobo et al. 2008). Thus, the desirable way to reliably test a model is by gathering independent data to evaluate predictions. Monitoring programs of alien species provide a great opportunity for a more independent evaluation by boosting data availability over space and time, helping to improve the evaluation approach (Barbet-Massin et al. 2018).

To overcome some of these limitations and investigate the range dynamics of alien species, we applied SDM including multiple predictors related to vectors of introduction and dispersal and correcting for potential error sources (Sillero and Barbosa 2021). We examined the distribution of four aquatic alien species from four different taxonomic groups (fish, reptiles, amphibians and crustaceans) deliberately introduced through different routes (i.e., ornamental trade, aquaculture, pet release). The aims were: i) to identify the main drivers of dispersal of alien freshwater species in Great Britain using detailed predictors that can give light into the invasion process and ii) to assess the power of SDMs to predict the invasion process using two types of evaluations including: a) the common cross-validation approach but using a temporal data splitting instead of random selection which is more realistic to recreate the invasion process and b) an independent data evaluation using the range shift of the species with the absolute newest records (during the last 6 years) to retrospectively predict current invasion patterns.

Methods

Study area and species

We used Great Britain as study area as, being an island, it represents a closed system that allows the study of invasion processes without the possible influx of freshwater species from adjacent areas. Great Britain was divided into grids with a 5 Km² resolution as in previous studies of freshwater species in large areas (Gallardo and Aldridge 2013; Fletcher et al. 2016; Rodrigues et al. 2016). The study area was therefore composed of 8,735 grid cells after removing cells with less than 70% of the grid area to avoid the inclusion of those cells with a high sea cover.

We included signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*) among the arthropods, the marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*) among the amphibians, the red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*) as a reptile, and the pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*) amongst the fish. The species had 982, 94, 125 and 164 grid occurrences respectively. These four species represented various taxonomic groups that were deliberately introduced in Great Britain at the end of the 19th century or beginning of the 20th century except for signal crayfish, with a contemporaneous introduction but also a high range expansion. Species distribution data were obtained from the National Biodiversity Network (NBNAtlas) using records between the date of introduction of each species and 2015 for the modelling process; therefore, including a time frame of more than 150 years depending on the species arrival (Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S2).

To control for sampling bias, we applied “systematic sampling” consisting in pooling occurrences in grids to avoid the effect of overrepresentation of records in oversampled areas, showing the higher performance among other procedures (Fourcade et al. 2014). Also, we assessed the sampling bias in the study area using the Target Group Sampling method (Phillips et al. 2009) by examining the grid cells with at least an occurrence of a non-native species under study or a native species within the same taxonomic group (i.e., fish, amphibians) to ensure that the grids included in our study had been sampled. Pseudo-absences and background locations are then more certain, for instance, if an area is considered as well sampled but the target species was missing (Phillips et al. 2009; Merow et al. 2013). For this purpose, we compared the distribution of the marsh frog with the distribution of the native *Rana temporaria* and *Bufo bufo* as well as the pike-perch with the *Salmo trutta*, *Salmo salar*, *Cobitis taenia*, *Cottus gobio* and *Alosa alosa*. The slider and the crayfish could not be reliably compared since there is no similar species of reptiles in the study area and the native crayfish (*Austropotamobius pallipes*) is threatened over the study area and its distribution is currently restricted.

Predictors

We used a combination of both environmental and anthropogenic variables, to assess the relative importance of the predictors for the alien species distribution as in other studies, (Gallardo and Aldridge 2015; Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2019; Chapman et al. 2020). Models were calibrated only in the invaded area as it has been considered the best approach for the study species in the study area (Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2019) avoiding extrapolation issues which have important implications for SDM methodologies (Yates et al. 2018). We included bioclimatic predictors due to the known effect of climate on the distribution of alien freshwater species (Britton et al. 2010; Bellard et al. 2013) (Suppl. material 1: tables S3, S4) and land use predictors within a 50 m buffer strip from each riverbank, using the hydrography map OS Open Rivers from the Ordnance Survey (www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk). Worldclim was used as climate database because it has shown higher performance in comparison with other databases (Datta et al. 2020; Jiménez-Valverde et al. 2021), it is the most widely used in macroecological studies (Poggio et al. 2018; Marchi et al. 2019) and it includes climate information from 1970 to 2000, covering a large number of occurrences in the study, dating back to 1935 (Suppl. material 1: table S2). Regarding the anthropogenic predictors, we included the distance to the closest city and population density as an indicator of human presence and pressure and road density as an indicator of human accessibility. We included predictors related to activities that are sources of introduction, dispersal and propagule pressure as the distance to the nearest port, to the nearest boat launch ramp, the distance to aquaculture facilities and to garden centres, as most of the species had an economical interest in aquaculture, sport fishing or as pets (Padilla and Williams 2004). We also included the Euclidean distance to the locality where the species were firstly introduced to account for any spatially correlated pattern of dispersal and the history of the invasion (Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2013). We extracted the mean values of all the variables in each grid cell using the zonal statistic tool in QGIS (QGIS Development Team 2016) and accounted for predictors' collinearity by including only predictor with a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) smaller than 10 (Dormann et al. 2013) (Suppl. material 1: table S4).

Model calibration and evaluation 1

For each species, we analysed the distribution using four different SDM algorithms including Generalised Additive Models [GAM (Hastie and Tibshirani 1990)], MaxEnt (Phillips et al. 2006), Generalized Linear Models [GLM (Hosmer and Lemeshow 2000)], Random Forest models [RF (Cutler et al. 2007)] and an ensemble model combining all of the preceding algorithms (Thuiller et al. 2009). GAMs were fitted using a logit link function (binomial family) and thin plate penalised regression splines (Wood 2017) using the 'mgcv' package (Wood 2017) for R. Maxent was implemented using 'dismo' package in R (Hijmans et al. 2017) and GLMs were fitted using the logit link function (binomial family) with the base function in R (R Development Core Team 2018). RF we implemented using regression with 500 trees and a "mtry" of 6 using the randomForest (Liaw and Wiener 2002) and 'caret' packages (Kuhn et al. 2020) in R. Ensemble models including the four algorithms were created using 'biomod2' package in R (Thuiller et al. 2016) and the ensemble was calculated by averaging model predictions weighted by ROC and TSS. Due to the variety of study species, the multitude of possible combinations of hyperparameters' values (Zeng et al. 2016) and the 1000 simulations performed for the null models (see below), the modelling resulted

highly computationally demanding, so we did not tune hyperparameters. However, we made sure the convergence and meaning of all the models. The use of multiple algorithms intends to reduce the uncertainty associated with the model selection and outputs (Marmion et al. 2009). One of the most important improvements of our methodological approach in comparison with other studies was the temporal validation (Schatz et al. 2017; Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2019). We split data as in cross-validation with 70% and 30% for training and testing, respectively but trained the models with the oldest records (summing up to 70% of the total distribution data) and evaluated them using the most recent records (the remaining 30% of records) to reconstruct the invasion pathways followed by the species (Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2013; Barbet-Massin et al. 2018) (Suppl. material 1: table S2). We also accounted for sampling bias (as above) and applied sorting bias correction by pairwise distance sampling (Hijmans 2012) using ‘dismo’ package in R to avoid the spatial autocorrelation between training and test data known to inflate evaluation metrics (Sillero and Barbosa 2021). Pseudo-absences (for GAM, GLM and RF) and background data (for MaxEnt) were randomly selected but with a high certainty of being real absences after detecting that the sampling effort was high with over 70% of the grid cells being sampled.

Model quality was assessed using True Skills Statistic [TSS (Allouche et al. 2006)] and the Area Under the Curve based on the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve [AUC, (Fielding and Bell 1997)] measures of accuracy commonly used in SDM. Since a low model performance is expected after bias correction, we applied null models for significance testing of presence-only SDM which is being increasingly applied to improve evaluation and to reduce the over-optimistic nature of cross-validation (Lima et al. 2022; Osborne et al. 2022). Therefore, in addition to these commonly applied discrimination metrics, we also built null models to test the differences in the accuracy measures between the real and null models of the SDMs assuming that their performance is random (Raes and ter Steege 2007; Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2019). For each species and algorithm combination, we obtained 1000 null models, each one with a different rearrangement of the predictors obtained by permutation. Then, we calculated the differences in the discrimination measures between the null and the real models by subtracting real model statistic value minus the null model 95 CI maximum value (thereafter ‘effect size’). Hence, positive values indicated better than null models (i.e., not random), whereas negative values indicated worse than null or random results.

Variable importance

We calculated the relative contribution of the predictor variables in the best model for each species. For MaxEnt, variable importance corresponded to the resulting contribution percentage supported by jack-knife variable importance analysis (Phillips 2017); for GAM, RF and GLM, we applied the VarImp function from the ‘caret’ package (Kuhn et al. 2020) and for the ensemble, the average of all the models was used and then the variables_importance function available in ‘biomod2’ package was applied (Thuiller et al. 2016). Partial-dependence plots were used to graphically examine relationships between the predictors and the distribution of each species.

Model predictive power (evaluation 2)

We evaluated models obtained in the previous steps using the range shift of the species in the same study area after six years (from January 2016 to December 2021) to investigate if the most recent spread of the alien species occurred in the

areas predicted by the models. This constitutes another improvement in the evaluation approach using independent data. For this purpose, we evaluated the model predictions with the data corresponding to the real range expansion of the species (i.e., new distribution records) during the last six years published from the same source (NBNAAtlas).

We calculated the accuracy of the models to predict the most recent spread of the species by calculating the area under curve AUC using 'modEvA' package in R (Barbosa et al. 2021). We also examined the probability values of the recently occupied localities by calculating the quartile of values corresponding to the sites of new occurrences to examine the expected correspondence of new invasions in areas of higher predicted suitability as in Barbet-Massin et al. (2018).

Results

Species distribution models

The best models explaining the species distribution according to the effect size (i.e., the difference between the real model and the highest 95CI values of the null models for both discrimination statistics) were obtained with GAM for the signal crayfish, the red-eared slider and pike-perch, and with MaxEnt for the marsh frog. (Suppl. material 1: table S5). Signal crayfish occurrences were explained by the relative contribution of the distance to ports (16%) followed by road density (12%) both with a positive relationship (Fig. 1 and Suppl. material 1: fig. S2.1). Temperature seasonality and precipitation seasonality (10%), referred to the standard deviation of the temperature and precipitation and were the most important climatic predictors for the signal crayfish, with 11% and 10% of relative contribution to the model, both with positive relationships. Distance to the first introduction record (8% relative contribution) was negatively related to the signal crayfish presence. Altitude positively affected the probability of occurrence (7.5%), until above 400 meters where the effect was negative (Suppl. material 1: fig. S2.1).

For the red-eared slider, isothermality (i.e., mean diurnal range divided by mean annual range of temperature) and temperature in the wettest quarter had the highest relative importance within the environmental variables (19% and 11% respectively) (Fig. 1). The increase of both decreased the probability of the alien turtle presence. Road density positively contributed to the probability of occurrence by 15% as well as the proximity to the introduction point by 14% (Suppl. material 1: fig. S2.2). The distance to garden centres negatively affected the slider occurrence with a 10% of relative importance.

The marsh frog had a distribution mainly marked by the distance to the first introduction site followed by the population density, with a relative importance of 62% and 14% and negative and positive relationships, respectively (Fig. 1 and Suppl. material 1: fig. S2.3). The remaining variance was explained by a small contribution from most of the rest of the variables.

For the pike-perch, distance to the first record had a relative importance of 23% followed by precipitation seasonality with 14% of importance, both decreasing the probability of its presence (Suppl. material 1: fig. S2.4). In contrast, temperature seasonality positively affected the presence of pike-perch with a relative importance of 13%. Among the anthropogenic variables, population density (11% of importance) and distance to garden centres (9.5%) affected the pike-perch's presence with negative and positive signs, respectively. Other variables such as altitude and grassland cover in the riverside also contributed to explain the pike-perch distribution.

Figure 1. Relative importance of environmental and anthropic predictors for the best model for each species. The crayfish icon represents the signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), the turtle icon represents the red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*), the frog icon corresponds to marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*) and the fish icon represents the pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*).

Model predictive power (evaluation 2)

Based on the predicted suitability for each species (Fig. 2), the prediction rate curves of AUC values of the models evaluated using the most recent range expansion of the species (i.e., from 2016 to 2021) were 0.826 for the signal crayfish, 0.853 for the red-eared slider, 0.935 for the marsh frog and 0.797 for the pike-perch (Fig. 3). Signal crayfish highly increased its distribution between 2016 and 2021 with 404 new occurrences and 71% of the new registers were recorded in areas with predicted values of suitability over the third quartile. Red-eared slider and the pike-perch had most of their new records (80% and 82% respectively) in areas with predicted probability values within the third quartile for the whole study area. The marsh frog, increased its distribution with new 61 records with 92% of them falling in areas with suitabilities over or within the third quartile.

Discussion

Our models were highly capable to predict the last range expansion of the species (last six years). Independent data for evaluation is desirable to measure the ability of the predicted areas to be occupied. Model calibration and evaluation 1 aimed to replicate the standard practice in SDM evaluation (cross-validation using 70% and 30% of the data for training and testing, respectively) but splitting datasets using the chronological information of the range expansion instead of a random selection. Our models provided better than random models but with relatively low values of performance. The reason for low values in model performance arose from the sorting bias correction. Spatial sorting bias is known to inflate evaluation metrics (Sillero and Barbosa 2021; Illanas et al. 2022) and generate model over-estimation (Veloz 2009; Hijmans 2012). Therefore, sorting bias correction overall reduced model performance since uncorrected models showed a strong bias in

Figure 2. Suitability maps for the best model for each species showing the occurrences until 2015 used for model training and testing and the occurrences from 2016 to 2021 to posterior evaluation of the range expansion. The crayfish icon represents the signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), the turtle icon represents the red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*), the frog icon corresponds to marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*) and the fish icon represents the pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*).

their predicted species patterns (Hertzog et al. 2014; Freeman et al. 2022). Nevertheless, the most relevant evaluation in this study is the one based on the real range expansion of the species after 6 years (evaluation 2) showing that models' predictions were highly accurate after independent data validation. This change in the

Figure 3. ROC plot of True Positive Rate (sensitivity) and False Positive Rate (1-specificity) with the AUC values calculated using the model predicted probabilities and the recent invasion of the a) signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), b) red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*), c) marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*) and d) pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*).

predictive ability is in agreement with Hertzog et al. (2014) that reported average differences in the AUC between sorting bias uncorrected and corrected models of 0.4, and the model with the lowest AUC but that was bias corrected, obtained the best performance after independent field data evaluation.

The distribution of alien species is affected by both climatic and anthropogenic variables. Human population density can be an indicator of non-native species propagule pressure (Copp et al. 2010), as confirmed by our results for marsh frog, pike-perch and red-eared slider occurrences, all favoured by high population density. Population density was the second most important predictor for the marsh frog distribution preceded by the distance to the introduction point, which indicates that the most populated areas not only promote their introduction but might also facilitate their establishment and expansion, for example via garden ponds (Vimercati et al. 2017), increasing the connectivity between populations in the absence of streams (Atobe et al. 2014). Population density as a predictor should be investigated in detail for management purposes, to identify the main points of entry or activities, as per se does not provide specific information on the activities or places that need to be regulated. Population density and the Human Footprint Index seem to shape the spatial distribution of biodiversity and also the presence of invasive species (Di Marco et al. 2013; Aronson et al. 2014; Gallardo et al. 2015; Dimitrakopoulos et al. 2017) which highlights the need to identify the specific vectors of secondary spread, such as flows of people, cars, trains or boats (Gilbert et al. 2004;

Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2021) or defining spatial proxies of human activities promoting species invasion (Chapman et al. 2020). This can be achieved by prioritising risk assessment approaches that rely less on invasion history (e.g., historical sources of species) and focus more on environmental change and the consequences of expanding trade routes or aquatic activities, that increase source pools of alien species (Seebens et al. 2018). The release of animals to the wild is more frequent in urban than in rural areas (Olden et al. 2005), a good example being the red-slider, which was in our study particularly abundant close to cities with more than 50k inhabitants. Yet, although urban areas host many alien species, and act as foci from which they can spread and invade surrounding natural areas (McLean et al. 2017), most of the distribution patterns of the species in our study were unrelated to distance to cities.

Road density and proximity to garden centres favoured the spread of the red-slider suggesting that this species was introduced deliberately as pets (Copp et al. 2005) in the areas most accessible to people (Hulme 2009). Distance to garden centres has previously been found to promote the introduction of imported turtles, which increases propagule pressure (Duggan et al. 2006; Copp et al. 2010). Another species potentially favoured by road density was the signal crayfish, whose presence was also driven by climatic conditions. Its ability to adapt to multiple climatic conditions has allowed this species to adapt to areas with higher temperature and precipitation seasonality, as well as to large rivers at low altitudes, which tends to facilitate the invasion of freshwater species (Gebauer et al. 2018). However, altitude might limit its distribution due to high flows associated with steep gradients in headwaters. This species tends to be located far from ports pointing to the species' tolerance to water salinity. Although ports are also located in estuarine waters, signal crayfish can only survive with salinity conditions below 14 PSU (Holdich et al. 1997) rarely common in British estuaries (van der Meer et al. 2016; Ownsworth et al. 2019).

Precipitation seasonality had a negative effect on pike-perch's presence, which indicates that this species is unable to cope with variable flow regimens. In fact, for this species, seasonal weather patterns have been reported to affect spawning success, egg survival and post-hatching survival (Kanno et al. 2016) and changes in flow reduce fish recruitment (Dutterer et al. 2013). High precipitation in the warmest months benefited pike-perch's presence which might be explained by the big size of the species, originally from large streams, that might be more affected than smaller fish by decreases in flow and habitat availability through an increase in competition (Rolls et al. 2012). Also, pike-perch prefers warm water which is why increasing temperature in the wettest months increased the presence of the species (Keskinen 2008). The influence of environmental drivers in the distribution of pike-perch is also reflected by its presence in less populated areas and far from garden centres, which might reflect a preference for more natural areas.

Most of the alien species we studied were more likely to be found closer to the places where they were first introduced, especially the marsh frog. This might be due to their limited ability to disperse due to climatic reasons. In this sense, further analysis is required to account for the type of dispersal followed by the different taxa. According to the importance of this predictor (i.e., "distance to the first records"), implementing management on areas surrounding the locations of the first introduction resulted highly important for all study species and supports the fact that effective early detection will facilitate the first management steps (Muha et al. 2017). Monitoring alien species over space and time provides data to develop time independent evaluations of the species' models, which is one of the biggest limitations in SDM (Araújo et al. 2005) due to the dependency between training and testing data, that leads to prediction errors (Roberts et al. 2017; Liu et al. 2020). The modelling procedure implemented in this study used the spatial records of

the species at earlier stages of invasion to calibrate the models and recent invasion records to evaluate them, can be applied with promising results (Barbet-Massin et al. 2018). In addition, we further conducted another evaluation using the range expansion in the last six years to realistically evaluate the predictive capacity of our models with independent data which constitutes a novel step in SDM for alien species. For all the species with a range expansion, the models were accurate in terms of AUC and correctly predicted the newly occupied localities, therefore, highlighting the usefulness of this approach.

Considering the most important anthropogenic predictors driving each species expansion together with the predictive risk maps (i.e., presented suitability maps, which help to identify those localities most vulnerable to be invaded next) can guide decision making to allocate resources and prioritising management actions to prevent the arrival of the species to new locations, especially to those places of conservation importance, with endangered species or in protected areas (Johovic et al. 2020), with biosecurity risks (Gallardo et al. 2022) or where high economic impacts are expected (Haubrock et al. 2021). Predicting species distributions to prioritise management is fundamental (Guillera-Aroita et al. 2015; Wood et al. 2018) and non-native species monitoring in many regions promote the availability of records for a convenient evaluation using SDM. Future steps should aim for detecting more specific human activities at spatial scales and with a higher impact to expand alien species.

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Author contributions

M.R-R. and C.G.L. conceived the idea. M.R-R. compiled and curated the data and M.R-R. and C.G.L. analysed the data. All authors interpreted the outputs, contributed to manuscript writing, gave approval for publication and agree to be accountable for any question related to this work.

Availability of data and material and Code availability

All data used is derived from public domain resources. A reference script is available as supporting information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary information

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: **figure S1**. Diagram of the workflow for Species Distribution Modelling in this study; **figure S2.1**. Response curves for signal crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*) according to GAM; **figure S2.2**. Response curves for red-eared slider (*Trachemys scripta*) according to GAM; **figure S2.3**. Response curves for marsh frog (*Pelophylax ridibundus*) according to MaxEnt. Negative values on the predictor, although unrealistic in some cases, resulted from the function projecting into the negative and positive range of values; **figure S2.4**. Response curves for pike-perch (*Sander lucioperca*) according to GAM; **table S1**. Characteristics of the species regarding the year and locality of introduction in the study area, the reason of their introduction, the way they commonly spread and their origin and functional type classification.; **table S2**. Number of occurrences and covered years used in each modelling step for the different species; **table S3**. Predictor variables used in the Species Distribution Models. Variables in bold had VIF scores smaller than 10 (Hairs et al. 1998) and were included in the Species Distribution Models; **table S4**. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for those predictors with VIF<10; **table S5**. True Skill Statistic (TSS) and Area Under the Curve (AUC) results for the models computed using four algorithms and the ensemble. Effect size corresponds to the difference between the real model and the null model 95 CI maximum value, calculated for both discrimination statistics.

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